

IMPACT OF STRESS ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AMONG UNDERGRADUATE NURSING STUDENTS COLLEGE OF NURSING

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Abstract

Introduction:

Stress is a dynamic interaction between a person and the environment, where it is a collection of the events or conditions in the environment of a person that keeps the mental, physical and psychological capabilities to test. It can be recognized as a collection of contemporary lifestyles, with a negative effect and adversely impairing the performance of an individual. Nursing students reported significant stress from coursework, assessments, and clinical practices.

Objectives:

To determine the impact of stress on academic performance and assess the contribution to stress among nursing students at the college of nursing female Nawabshah.

Methodology:

The study was a descriptive cross-sectional design. The sample size was 132 and conducted from September to November 2025 at college of nursing female Nawabshah.

Result: T

he current study shows the majority of participant were singled had 77% moderate stress. The mean age was 22.32(± 2.47), regarding marital status most of participants were unmarried 91.7% and the mean GPA was 3.49(± 0.409), and the maximum subject have limited time to prepared their classes 50 (37.8%), in addition a large number of students felt overwhelmed by the amount of coursework 62(46.9%). Further larger number of study subject were felling stress from clinical supervisor's expectation 55(41.6%) and the high proportion of students felt stress when they cannot manage the time 48(36.3%).

Conclusion:

This study concluded that students experience moderate academic stress, due to academic activity, and facing difficulty in time management.

INTRODUCTION

Nursing students often face a lot of stress because their studies are very difficult in the academic setting. Nursing students reported significant stress from coursework, assignments, and clinical placements.(1) Stress is a collection of the events or conditions in the environment of a person that keeps the mental, physical and psychological capabilities to test. Stress is described as one of the most significant challenges of the modern society. (2) Nursing students face even more stress compared to other university students because they also spend many hours in clinical practice, exposure to patients' condition, and the expectation to perform clinical procedures properly and independently.(3) perceive significant stresses because of external demands, high pressures, and expectations introduced by family, friends and even themselves(4) Prolonged high stress negatively impact on psychological health, academic performance, and well-being. (5) Several studies reported that First-year students are worried about adjusting to a new environment, second-year students feel stress from clinical, academic performance and time management, and final-year students worry about exams, license, and jobs. First-year students represent higher academic stress compared to final-year students. (6) Moderate stress noted problem focused coping reduced stress impact. (7) Academic overwork negatively correlated with personal competence, psychological well-being, and GPA.(8) 62% of nursing students experience stress, mostly at moderate levels. (9) Stress levels increased over 5 years, reaching the highest point in mid-program with exams and workload. (10) Stress and low personal competence significantly predicted lower academic performance. (11) Moderate high stress affects professional identity, interventions for suggested high-risk profiles.(12) Stress, anxiety, and depression predicted burnout. (13)

Significance of Study:

Nursing students are faced to multiple stressors due to the demanding of their nursing education, which includes both academic learning and clinical practice. This study will fill this gap by focusing on female BSN students in one institution and directly testing the relationship between stress and academic performance.

Objectives of Study:

Measure the level of academic stress among BSN students using Academic Stress Inventory and identify the major sources of stress among nursing students at College of Nursing, Female Nawabshah.

Material & Methods

This study was cross sectional study, which is conducted from September to November 2025 at College of Nursing, Female Nawabshah. The sample size was determined using the Rao-soft sample size calculator at a 95% confidence level, 5% margin of error, 50% response distribution, and a target population of 200 nursing students. The required sample size was calculated as 132 students.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Nursing Students 2nd year (4th semester) 3rd year (6th semester) and 4th year (8th semester) enrolled in the BSN program
2. Registered during the study period
3. Willing to take part in the research

Exclusion Criteria

1. Students who are on leave during the study
2. Students who self-report any diagnosed psychiatric illness.
3. Nursing Students Year -I .

Tools for Data Collection:

A self-report questionnaire used to measure a student's perceived stress levels in an academic environment, which is based on the (Academic Stress Inventory ASI). It included of two sections: demographic details (age, year of study, marital status, GPA) and 15 items measuring stress on 5-point Likert scale 1(Never) to 5(Always). The total score ranges from 55 to 75, and a score of 35 or above shows academic stress in students. Questionnaires were distributed to BSN students during free time in classrooms. The purpose of study was explained and written concern form was taken. Written informed consent was obtained from each student prior to participation. The students were instructed to complete the questionnaires on the spot to ensure completeness and accuracy of responses. The researcher also assured the

participants that all information provided would remain strictly confidential. Data were processed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). First demographic variables, stress scores, and GPA were recorded into SPSS. Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, frequencies, and percentages) were used to summarize the demographic information and stress levels. Stress

scores were further classified into low, moderate, and high categories. Inferential statistics were applied using the Pearson correlation coefficient to test the relationship between stress levels and academic performance (GPA). A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Result

Table No.1 Demographic characteristics

Ser.	Item	Frequency (percentage)
1.	Distribution of Age of Subject	
	Minimum Age	19.00
	Maximum Age	35.00
	Mean	22.32
	S.D ±	2.47
2.	Distribution of Marital status	
	Single	121(91.7%)
	Married	11(8.3%)
3.	Year of Studying	
	First Year	34(25.8%)
	Second Year	37(28%)
	Third Year	31(23.5%)
	Fourth Years	30(22.7%)
4.	Academic Performance (GPA)	
	Minimum GPA	2.04
	Maximum GPA	6.39
	Mean GPA	3.49
	S.D ±	.409

Table No.1 showed demographic characteristics of the study participant. Age of subject in which minimum age 19, maximum age 35, mean 22.32 and S.D ± 2.47, regarding marital status majority of participate were single 121(91.7%), while married 11(8.3%). In terms Year of study, the participants of

first year n=34(25.8%), second year n=37(28%), third year n=31(23.5%), and fourth year n=30(22.7%). Concerning academic performance, minimum GPA 2.04, Maximum GPA 6.39, the Mean GPA was 3.49 with a S.D ±.409.

Table No.2 distribution of stress item score with age and GPA

stress item score	Correlation value	p-value
Age	.158	.031
GPA	-.008	.912

Table No.2 showed that the correlation between age and stress item score was slightly positive ($r= 0.158$,

$p=.031$), while correlation between GPA and stress score was no significant associated ($r=-.008$, $p= .912$).

Table No. 3 distribution of stress item score with marital status and year of study

Stress item score	Low stress	Moderate stress	High stress	P value
Marital Status				
Single	25	77	19	.003
Married	2	6	3	
Years of Study				
1 st year	4	23	7	.017
2 nd year	15	20	2	
3 rd year	3	22	6	
4 th year	5	18	7	
Total	27	83	22	

Table No.3 presented that stress item score of the study participants. The majority of Marital status in which 25 low stress, 77 moderate stress, and 19 high stress in the single participants, where 2 low stress, 6 moderate stress and 3 high stress in the married participants. Year of study included 1st year stress item score was 4 low stress, 23 moderate stress and 7

high stress, 2nd year stress score was 15 low stress, 20 moderate stress, 2 high stress, 3rd year stress score was 5 low stress, 18 moderate stress and 7 high stress, 4th year stress score was 5 low stress, 18 moderate stress and 7 high stress. The total stress item score of study year was 27 less, 83 moderate and 22 high stress of nursing student.

Table No.04.Distribution of variable related to acadmic and assignment of age of subject:

SNo.	Item	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Alwayes	P value
1	I feel overwhelmed by the amount of coursework I have to complete.	18 (13.6%)	15 (11.3%)	62 (46.9%)	16 (12.1%)	21 (11.9%)	.005
2	I do not have enough time to prepare for my classes.	50 (37.8%)	33 (25.0%)	32 (24.2%)	13 (9.8%)	4 (3.0%)	.002
3	I have difficulty balancing study with other responsibilities	29 (21.9%)	26 (19.6%)	45 (34.0%)	12 (9.0%)	20 (15.1%)	.051
4	I feel nervous before taking exams.	12 (9.0%)	21 (15.9%)	43 (32.5%)	23 (17.4%)	33 (25%)	.031
5	I worry about getting poor grades.	19 (14.1%)	16 (12.1%)	40 (30.3%)	9 (6.8%)	48 (36.3%)	.025
6	Deadlines for assignments cause me stress.	21 (15.9%)	19 (14.3%)	53 (40.1%)	19 (14.3%)	9 (18.9%)	.013

7	I feel stressed while dealing with patients in the clinical area.	37 (28%)	14 (10.6%)	53 (40.1%)	19 (14.3%)	9 (6.8%)	.080
8	I am worried about making mistakes during clinical practice	17 (12.8%)	29 (21.9%)	45 (34.0%)	17 (12.8%)	24 (18.1%)	.045
9	The expectations of my clinical supervisors are stressful.	33 (25%)	10 (7.5%)	55 (41.6%)	16 (12.1%)	18 (13.6%)	.013

Item No.1, subject reported that I feel overwhelmed by the amount of coursework I have to complete never 18(13.6%), rarely 15 (11.3%), sometimes 62 (46.9%), often 16 (12.1%), and always 21 (11.9%), which significant association with age ($p= .005$).Item No.2, Subject reported that I do not have enough time to prepare for my classes never 50 (37.8%), rarely 33(25%), sometimes 32 (24.2%), often 13(9.8%), and always 4(3.0%), which significant association with age ($p=.002$). Item No.3, subject reported that I have difficulty balancing study with other responsibilities never 29(21.9%), rarely 26(19.6%), sometimes 45(34.0%), often 12 (9.0%), and always 20(15.1%) which showed no significant association with age ($p=.051$). Item No. 4, subject reported that I feel nervous before taking exams. Never 12(9.0%), rarely 21(15.9%), sometimes 43(32.5%), often 23(17.4%), and always 33(25%), which significant association with age ($p=.031$). Item No.5, subject reported that I worry about getting poor grades. Never 19(14.1%), rarely 16(12.1%), sometimes 40(30.3%), often 9(6.8%), and always

48(36.3%), which significant association with age ($p=.025$). Item No.6, subject reported that Deadlines for assignments cause me stress. Never 21(15.9%), rarely 19(14.3%), sometimes 39(29.5%), often 28(21.2%), and always 25(18.9%), which significant association with age ($p=.013$). Item No.7, subject reported that I feel stressed while dealing with patients in the clinical area. Never 37(28.0%), rarely 14(10.6%), sometimes 53(40.1%), often 19(14.3%), and always 9(6.8%), which showed no significant association with age ($p=.080$).Item No.8, subject reported that I am worried about making mistakes during clinical practice. Never 17(12.8%), rarely 29(21.9%), sometimes 45(34.0), often 17(12.8%), and always 24(18.1%), which significant association with age ($p=.045$).Item No.9, subject reported that the expectations of my clinical supervisors are stressful. Never 33(25%), rarely 10(7.5%), sometimes 55(41.6%), often 16(12.1%), and always 18(13.6%), which significant association with age ($p=.013$).

Table No.05.Distribution of personal issue and time management of age of subject:

SNo.	Item	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always	Pvalue
1.	I feel stressed by peer competition in my class.	43 (32.5%)	22 (16.6%)	40 (30.3%)	16 (12.1%)	11 (8.3%)	.018
2.	I find it stressful to communicate with teachers or supervisors.	44 (33.3%)	13 (9.8%)	43 (32.5%)	15 (11.3%)	17 (12.8%)	.006

3.	I feel I lack support from my peers or teachers.	46 (34.8%)	14 (10.6%)	43 (32.5%)	15 (11.3%)	14 (10.6%)	.055
4.	I do not have enough time for rest and relaxation due to academic work.	25 (18.9%)	12 (9.0%)	58 (43.9%)	10 (7.5%)	22 (16.6%)	.010
5.	I feel stress when I cannot manage my time properly.	16 (12.1%)	24 (18.1%)	48 (36.3%)	22 (16.6%)	22 (16.6%)	.035
6.	Academic responsibilities interfere with my personal and family life.	33 (25.0%)	18 (13.6%)	42 (31.8%)	16 (12.1%)	23 (17.4%)	.060

Item No.10, subject reported that I feel stressed by peer competition in my class. Never 43(32.5%), rarely 22(16.6%), sometimes 40(30.3%), often 16(12.1%), and always 11(8.33%), which significant association with age ($p=.018$). Item No.11, subject reported that I find it stressful to communicate with teachers or supervisors. Never 44(33.3%), rarely 13(9.84%), sometimes 43(32.5%), often 15(11.3%), and always 17(12.8%), which significant association with age ($p=.006$). Item No.12, I feel I lack support from my peers or teachers. Never 46(34.8%), rarely 14(10.6%), sometimes 43(32.5%), often 15(11.3%), and 14(10.6%), which showed no significant association with age ($p=.055$). Item No.13, subject reported that I do not have enough time for rest and

relaxation due to academic work. Never 12(9.0%), rarely 58(43.9%), sometimes 10(7.57%), often 22(16.1%) and always 23(17.4%), which significant association with age ($p=.010$). Item No.14, subject reported that I feel stress when I cannot manage my time properly. Never 16(12.1%), rarely 24(18.1%), sometimes 48(36.3%), often 22(16.6%), and always 22(16.6%), which significant association with age ($p=.035$). Item No. 15, subject reported that academic responsibilities interfere with my personal and family life. Never 33(25%), rarely 18(13.6%), sometimes 42(31.8%), often 16(12.1%) and always 23(17.4%), which showed no significant association with age ($p=.060$).

Table No.6.Distribution of variable related to accademic and assignment of Marital status of subject:

SNo.	Item	Never	Rarely	Sometime s	Often	Alwayes	<i>P</i> value
1	I feel overwhelmed by the amount of coursework I have to complete.	18 (13.6%)	15 (11.3%)	62 (46.9%)	16 (12.1%)	21 (11.9%)	.035
2	I do not have enough time to prepare for my classes.	50 (37.8%)	33 (25.0%)	32 (24.2%)	13 (9.8%)	4 (3.0%)	.021
3	I have difficulty balancing study with other responsibilities	29 (21.9%)	26 (19.6%)	45 (34.0%)	12 (9.0%)	20 (15.1%)	.398

4	I feel nervous before taking exams.	12 (9.0%)	21 (15.9%)	43 (32.5%)	23 (17.4%)	33 (25%)	.042
5	I worry about getting poor grades.	19 (14.1%)	16 (12.1%)	40 (30.3%)	9 (6.8%)	48 (36.3%)	.015
6	Deadlines for assignments cause me stress.	21 (15.9%)	19 (14.3%)	53 (40.1%)	19 (14.3%)	9 (6.8%)	.630
7	I feel stressed while dealing with patients in the clinical area.	37 (28%)	14 (10.6%)	53 (40.1%)	19 (14.3%)	9 (6.8%)	.323
8	I am worried about making mistakes during clinical practice	17 (12.8%)	29 (21.9%)	45 (34.0%)	17 (12.8%)	24 (18.1%)	.050
9	The expectations of my clinical supervisors are stressful.	33 (25%)	10 (7.5%)	55 (41.6%)	16 (12.1%)	18 (13.6%)	.033

Item No.1, subject reported that I feel overwhelmed by the amount of coursework I have to complete never 18(13.6%), rarely 15 (11.3%), sometimes 62 (46.9%), often 16 (12.1%), and always 21 (11.9%), which significant association with marital status ($p=.035$). Item No.2, Subject reported that I do not have enough time to prepare for my classes never 50 (37.8%), rarely 33(25%), sometimes 32 (24.2%), often 13(9.8%), and always 4(3.0%), which significant association with marital status ($p=.021$).Item No.3, subject reported that I have difficulty balancing study with other responsibilities never 29(21.9%), rarely 26(19.6%), sometimes 45(34.0%), often 12 (9.0%), and always 20(15.1%) which showed no significant association with marital status ($p=.398$). Item No. 4, subject reported that I feel nervous before taking exams. Never 12(9.0%), rarely 21(15.9%), sometimes 43(32.5%), often 23(17.4%), and always 33(25%), which significant association with marital status ($p=.042$). Item No.5, subject reported that I worry about getting poor grades. Never 19(14.1%), rarely 16(12.1%), sometimes 40(30.3%), often 9(6.8%), and always

48(36.3%), which significant association with marital status ($p=.015$).Item No.6, subject reported that Deadlines for assignments cause me stress. Never 21(15.9%), rarely 19(14.3%), sometimes 39(29.5%), often 28(21.2%), and always 25(18.9%), which showed no significant association with marital status ($p=.630$). Item No.7, subject reported that I feel stressed while dealing with patients in the clinical area. Never 37(28.0%), rarely 14(10.6%), sometimes 53(40.1%), often 19(14.3%), and always 9(6.8%), which showed no significant association with marital status ($p=.323$).Item No.8, subject reported that I am worried about making mistakes during clinical practice. Never 17(12.8%), rarely 29(21.9%), sometimes 45(34.0%), often 17(12.8%), and always 24(18.1%), which significant association with marital status ($p=.050$). Item No.9, subject reported that the expectations of my clinical supervisors are stressful. Never 33(25%), rarely 10(7.5%), sometimes 55(41.6%), often 16(12.1%), and always 18(13.6%), which significant association with marital status ($p=.033$).

Table No.7.Distribution of personal issue and time management of Marital status of subject:

SNo.	Item	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always	Pvalue
1.	I feel stressed by peer competition in my class.	43 (32.5%)	22 (16.6%)	40 (30.3%)	16 (12.1%)	11 (8.3%)	.011
2.	I find it stressful to communicate with teachers or supervisors.	44 (33.3%)	13 (9.8%)	43 (32.5%)	15 (11.3%)	17 (12.8%)	.040
3.	I feel I lack support from my peers or teachers.	46 (34.8%)	14 (10.6%)	43 (32.5%)	15 (11.3%)	14 (10.6%)	.027
4.	I do not have enough time for rest and relaxation due to academic work.	25 (18.9%)	12 (9.0%)	58 (43.9%)	10 (7.5%)	22 (16.6%)	.036
5.	I feel stress when I cannot manage my time properly.	16 (12.1%)	24 (18.1%)	48 (36.3%)	22 (16.6%)	22 (16.6%)	.041
6.	Academic responsibilities interfere with my personal and family life.	33 (25.0%)	18 (13.6%)	42 (31.8%)	16 (12.1%)	23 (17.4%)	.019

Item No.10, subject reported that I feel stressed by peer competition in my class. Never 43(32.5%), rarely 22(16.6%), sometimes 40(30.3%), often 16(12.1%), and always 11(8.33%), which significant association with marital status ($p=.011$). Item No.11, subject reported that I find it stressful to communicate with teachers or supervisors. Never 44(33.3%), rarely 13(9.84%), sometimes 43(32.5%), often 15(11.3%), and always 17(12.8%), which significant association with marital status ($p=.040$). Item No.12, I feel I lack support from my peers or teachers. Never 46(34.8%), rarely 14(10.6%), sometimes 43(32.5%), often 15(11.3%), and 14(10.6%), which significant association with marital status ($p=.027$).Item No.13, subject reported that I

do not have enough time for rest and relaxation due to academic work. Never 12(9.0%), rarely 58(43.9%), sometimes 10(7.57%), often 22(16.1%) and always 23(17.4%), which significant association with marital status ($p=.036$).Item No.14, subject reported that I feel stress when I cannot manage my time properly. Never 16(12.1%), rarely 24(18.1%), sometimes 48(36.3%), often 22(16.6%), and always 22(16.6%), which significant association with marital status ($p=.041$).Item No. 15, subject reported that academic responsibilities interfere with my personal and family life. Never 33(25%), rarely 18(13.6%), sometimes 42(31.8%), often 16(12.1%) and always 23(17.4%), which significant association with marital status ($p=.019$).

Table No.8.Distribution of acadmic workload of study year of subject:

SNo.	Item	Never	Rarely	Sometime s	Often	Always	P value
1	I feel overwhelmed by the amount of coursework I have to complete.	18 (13.6%)	15 (11.3%)	62 (46.9%)	16 (12.1%)	21 (11.9%)	.033
2	I do not have enough time to prepare for my classes.	50 (37.8%)	33 (25.0%)	32 (24.2%)	13 (9.8%)	4 (3.0%)	.005
3	I have difficulty balancing study with other responsibilities	29 (21.9%)	26 (19.6%)	45 (34.0%)	12 (9.0%)	20 (15.1%)	.002
4	I feel nervous before taking exams.	12 (9.0%)	21 (15.9%)	43 (32.5%)	23 (17.4%)	33 (25%)	.023
5	I worry about getting poor grades.	19 (14.1%)	16 (12.1%)	40 (30.3%)	9 (6.8%)	48 (36.3%)	.009
6	Deadlines for assignments cause me stress.	21 (15.9%)	19 (14.3%)	53 (40.1%)	19 (14.3%)	9 (18.9%)	.013
7	I feel stressed while dealing with patients in the clinical area.	37 (28%)	14 (13.6%)	53 (40.1%)	19 (14.3%)	9 (6.8%)	.006
8	I am worried about making mistakes during clinical practice	17 (12.8%)	29 (21.9%)	45 (34.0%)	17 (12.8%)	24 (18.1%)	.043
9	The expectations of my clinical supervisors are stressful.	33 (25%)	10 (7.5%)	55 (41.6%)	16 (12.1%)	18 (13.6%)	.019

Item No.1, subject reported that I feel overwhelmed by the amount of coursework I have to complete never 18(13.6%), rarely 15 (11.3%), sometimes 62 (46.9%), often 16 (12.1%), and always 21 (11.9%), which significant association with study year ($p=.0.033$).Item No.2, Subject reported that I do not have enough time to prepare for my classes never 50 (37.8%), rarely 33(25%), sometimes32 (24.2%), often 13(9.8%), and always 4(3.0%), which significant association with study year ($p=.0.005$).Item No.3, subject reported that I have difficulty balancing study with other responsibilities

never 29(21.9%), rarely 26(19.6%), sometimes 45(34.0%), often12 (9.0%), and always 20(15.1%) which significant association with study year ($p=0.002$).Item No. 4, subject reported that I feel nervous before taking exams. Never 12(9.0%), rarely 21(15.9%), sometimes 43(32.5%), often 23(17.4%), and always 33(25%), which significant association with study year ($p=0.023$).Item No.5, subject reported that I worry about getting poor grades. Never 19(14.1%), rarely 16(12.1%), sometimes 40(30.3%), often 9(6.8%), and always 48(36.3%), which significant association with study year

($p=0.009$). Item No.6, subject reported that Deadlines for assignments cause me stress. Never 21(15.9%), rarely 19(14.3%), sometimes 39(29.5%), often 28(21.2%), and always 25(18.9%), which significant association with study year ($p=0.013$). Item No.7, subject reported that I feel stressed while dealing with patients in the clinical area. Never 37(28.0%), rarely 14(10.6%), sometimes 53(40.1%), often 19(14.3%), and always 9(6.8%), which significant association with study year ($p=0.006$). Item No.8, subject reported that I am worried about making mistakes during clinical practice. Never 17(12.8%), rarely 29(21.9%), sometimes 45(34.0), often 17(12.8%), and always 24(18.1%), which significant association with study year ($p=0.043$). Item No.9, subject reported that the expectations of my clinical supervisors are stressful. Never 33(25%), rarely 10(7.5%), sometimes 55(41.6%), often 16(12.1%), and always 18(13.6%), which significant association with study year ($p=0.019$).

Discussion

This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted to examine the impact of stress on academic performance from undergraduate students at the College of Nursing (Female), Nawabshah. The study included 132 students. The participants' mean grade point average (GPA) was ($3.49 \text{ SD} \pm 0.409$), which is higher than the ($3.13 \text{ SD} \pm 0.42$) compared with Iftikhar ahmed et al. (2025) in KPK, Pakistan.(14) The current study reported that mean age of the participants was ($22.32, \text{SD} \pm 2.47$), this result is comparable to that of Nazia Noreen et al. (2023), who found that nursing students had a mean age of ($21.4, \text{SD} \pm 2.2$). (15)(16) The current study reported that (92.42%) majority of participants were not married. This result higher than the finding is compared with Hanif ullah et al. (2024), where (66.22%) of the participants were single.(17)(18) The current study reported that the majority of undergraduate nursing students were young and unmarried, with respect to the year of study, the distribution of participants was relatively balanced (25.1%) were 1st year, (28%) 2nd year, (23.5%) 3rd year and (22.7%) 4th year students. Nermen abdelftah Mohamed et al. (2024) study, which found a similar distribution across academic years, (23.9%) were 1st year students while (30.1%), of 2nd year (23.5%) of

3rd year and (22.1%) 4th year students were participated .(1) (19) The current study reported that a significant association between age and feeling overwhelmed by the coursework ($p=.005$) this study align with the study by Shaheerah Yousef andargeerly et al. (2024), which also reported a significant associated between academic workload and emotional exhaustion ($p=0.006$). (20)(21) The current study reported that age was significantly associated with insufficient time to prepared for classes ($p=0.002$). This study compared with Fatima khatti et al. (2025), who found a significant correlation between stress and academic performance related time constraints ($p=0.002$). (22)(23) The current study reported that (34%) of participants were difficulty balanced studies with their other responsibilities. This finding compared with Afsha bibi et al.(2024), who found that (24.3%) of students felt stressed because it was hard to keep up with work or balancing academic demands with work or personal responsibilities.(24)

The current study reported that ($p=.031$) participants were felt nervous before test quarries and exam, this finding compared with shaheerah Yousef andargeerly et al. (2024), ($p=0.827$) of test or exam stress.(20) The current study reported that poor grades was significantly associated with age ($p=.025$). This study compared with Hanif ullah et al.(2025), who found no significant link between academic stress and worry about grades ($p=0.319$). (17)(25) The current study reported that deadlines for assignments caused stress among participants, however, the association was statistically ($p=.013$). This study compared with Rawhia falah dogham et al.(2024), who found ($p=0.001$) associated with stress from assignment and workload.(26) The current study reported that ($p=.080$) participants were stressed while dealing with patients in the clinical area. This study compared with Rawhia falah dogham et al. (2024), who found ($p=0.093$) of stress from taking care of patients, due to cultural or communication barriers.(26) The current study reported that ($p=.045$) participant were faced challenges about making mistakes during clinical practice. The study compared with hanif ullah et al. (2025), ($p=0.029$) of the pressure of clinical practice quality due to lack of practices and knowledge.(17) The current study reported that ($p=.018$) participants were feel stressed by peer

competition in their class group task. This study compared with Rawhia falah dogham et al. (2024), who reported ($p=0.002$) stress from peer and daily life.(26) The current study reported that ($p=.006$) participants were stressed to communicate with teacher or supervisor. This study compared with Hanif ullah et al. (2025), who reported ($p=0.009$) of stress from teacher and nursing staff, due to low confidence level.(17) The current study reported that ($p=.055$) participants were felt lack support from their peers or teachers. This finding compared with hanif ullah et al.(2025), who reported ($p=0.707$) feeling of stress when teacher instruction is unclear.(17) The current study reported that ($p=.010$) participants had not enough time for rest and relaxation due to academic work. This finding compared with Ashfaq ahmad et al. (2023), ($p=0.05$) of stress related sleep disturbance was significantly associated with academic performance.(27) The current study reported that ($p=.035$) participants had some trouble when they couldn't manage their time properly, this finding compared with Shaherah Yousef andergeerly et al. (2024), who reported ($p=0.004$) of time management stress, due to personal responsibilities.(20)(28) The current study reported that ($p=.060$) participants were academic responsibilities interfere with their personal. This finding compared with Zara AI Mohsen (2023), who reported ($p=0.010$) of stress from the effect of the academic workload and environment.(29) The current study reported that, single nursing students had a higher number of moderated stress scores 77 than married students. This finding compared with Saira Ramzan et al. (2024), who reported unmarried students had a higher number of severe stress scores 28 than married students, supporting the association between marital status and academic stress. The higher stress levels observed among unmarried nursing students may be attributed to increased academic competition, grater performance pressure, and limited emotional and social support. (30)(31)

Conclusion:

This study concluded that the most nursing students experiences moderate academic stress, due to academic activity and facing time management, which measured by Academic Stress Inventory scale (ASI).

Recommendation:

This study recommended that Future studies should include both gender male and female nursing students to compared stress levels. A larger sample size and students from different nursing institutes should be included to make the results more general. There is need to conduct the time management skills among undergraduate nursing student.

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